

8T – The Coupling Constants Series and the Invariance of the Electron

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Abstract:

By analyzing the coupling constants series and comparing it to ideas of other theories – such as string theory, which associate a new particle to a new string vibration – it is possible to analyze those ideas in a new light. In particular, it is possible to show that if that were in fact the case, there would be infinite number of coupling constants.

Introduction

First, we can represent the original equation, which regard Bosonic fields to be net curvature on the varying Lorentz manifold. Those Bosons are isomorphic to prime numbers or one - $\mathbb{P} \cup (+1)$, and propagating from matter clusters destabilized by the majestic (3), which is the electron, from the second element and above.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.21)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.3)$$

Suppose the idea of string theory was in fact correct, and each new slight variation of the invariant three would account a new particle. What are the implicit assumptions and results of such an idea? The first is slight or intense variations of the total magnitude of each coupling constant magnitude. In previous paper, we allowed slight variations toward pi but the key point was that the electron stayed as itself, it did not vary to a new particle. In other words, the electron is invariant while its shape does not. It is almost a perfect circle as it aspires pi, but even if it is to vary to pi, it is still the electron. If it were not the case, we would have been already observing a large variety of electrons which is not the case. That is as far as one knows there are only three variations including the electron itself – the Muon and the Tao, which differ in mass and isomorphic to each generation.

The Muon and the Tao in other words differ in the amount of curvature converged into the invariant three. That is the definition of mass in our theory. Since the electron is omitted from the nuclei, a cluster of Quarks, which themselves have more arbitrary curvature converging there could be a proportion between the amounts of curvature of each hadronic cluster of each generation to the electron like particle. The main difference between the 8T and string theory in that context is that even though it is possible for the electron to vary in nature, there is a clear cutting symmetry and the electron it itself in all times, excluding the mass generation pattern. Such a construction is freeing us from ever trying to predict the motion of this element, in contrast to string theory that tried to do it for over 50 years without success. The Muon and the Tao could also represented using the invariant three if the electric coupling magnitude is the same for all generations. If it is not the case, and for second and generation there is different magnitudes for each coupling term, which is not the case as far as one knows, than there should be a noticeable scalar multiple change in the invariant three and in the net curvature, i.e. the bosonic fields. For second generation:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + M * (3)] + 5$$

In addition, for third generation:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + N * M * (3)] + 5$$

$$M \cap N \in \mathbb{R}$$

If the coupling constants is same for all generations, than the invariant three is itself in each generation representation, and all the three generations can be represented in the same form, as in equation (1.21). Slight variations/vibrations does not change the electron from itself. Just imagine that nature would associate a new particle to each new slight arbitrary variation on the electron curvature ripple, we would have no coupling series and no standard model. Overall, the number of bosons and families is infinite, but it is much "smaller infinity" than the infinity suggested by string theory. For example for Bosons, it is restricted to prime numbers, and next particle should stand at 1/850 and in string theory there is not restriction at all, nor any predictions of any sort at the energy levels we can reach today.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)